

Greening the Digital Landscape: Investigating the Impact of Green Marketing Mix on Value Perception and E-commerce Purchase Intentions for Energy-Saving Electronic Goods

Fermatika Oktavia Hanna^{a*} & Nila Rahayu^b

^a Fakultas Budaya, Manajemen & Bisnis Universitas Pendidikan Mandalika, Jl. Pemuda No.59A Dasan Agung Baru, Kota Mataram, NTB 83125, Mataram, Indonesia

^b Fakultas Ekonomi & Bisnis Universitas Mataram, Jl. Majapahit No.62 Gomong, Kota Mataram, NTB 83125, Mataram, Indonesia

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Green Marketing Mix
Value Perception
Purchase Intentions

ABSTRACT

This research investigates the influence of green marketing mix, value perception, and purchase intention on energy-efficient electronic products in the city of Mataram. The study aims to measure the impact of green marketing mix on value perception and purchase intention through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. The research sample consists of 100 respondents who are active users of the e-commerce platform and have made purchases of energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. Respondent selection was done using purposive sampling method. Data analysis included instrument validity testing using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and reliability testing using Cronbach's Alpha. Subsequently, the data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) techniques with the smartPLS application. The research results indicate that green marketing mix has a positive and significant influence on value perception and also has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention. Furthermore, value perception also has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention. The analysis results demonstrate that indirectly, green marketing mix has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention through its impact on value perception. This research provides a deeper understanding of how sustainable marketing strategies can affect consumer preferences and behavior when purchasing energy-efficient electronic products through e-commerce platforms in Mataram.

1. Introduction

In this modern era, the development of digital technology has had a significant impact on various aspects of human life, including shopping through e-commerce platforms. On the other hand, awareness of environmental issues is also increasing, in line with a shift in societal mindset towards a more sustainable lifestyle. In this context, energy-saving electronic goods have become a primary focus, given their substantial influence on energy consumption and environmental impact.

In efforts to address environmental challenges and enhance a company's image, sustainable marketing strategies, known as green marketing, have become a crucial concern. This issue emerged as one of the most critical areas for marketing management in the 1990s (Cobb-Walgren, Ruble & Donthu, 1995). The concept of green marketing mix is an approach that encompasses various marketing elements, such as environmentally-friendly products, fair pricing, efficient distribution, and promotion that supports sustainability values (Mahmoud, 2018).

Green consumerism refers to the recycling, purchasing, and use of environmentally-friendly products with minimal impact on the environment (Rehman & Khyzer, 2013). According to Ashoush & Kortam (2022), using all four green marketing strategies simultaneously is the best approach to stimulate consumer purchase intent. Additionally, Chan & Lau (2000) confirmed in their research that green marketing strategies indeed have a positive impact on consumer purchase intent.

In the context of the green marketing mix, Kotler & Keller (2012) indicate that elements such as green products, fair pricing, efficient distribution, and sustainable promotion can influence consumers' perceptions of products. These perceptions create a positive evaluation of the product's value, known as value perception. Further research by Steg et al., (2014) shows that a positive value perception of environmentally-friendly products can motivate purchase intent.

* Corresponding author. Fakultas Budaya, Manajemen & Bisnis Universitas Pendidikan Mandalika, Jl. Pemuda No.59A Dasan Agung Baru, NTB 83125, Indonesia.

E-mail addresses: fermatika.oh@gmail.com (F. O. Hanna).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8318735>

Received 1 August 2023; Received in revised form 8 August 2023; Accepted 15 August 2023

Available online 17 August 2023

0000-0000/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Jurnal SELANDIR. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Green marketing mix directly influences consumer value perception (Prothero & Fitchett, 2000). Kotler & Keller (2012) suggest that elements of the green marketing mix emphasizing sustainability aspects, such as sustainable promotion and green products, can motivate consumers to perceive a product as a choice that provides positive environmental benefits. Consequently, consumers are more likely to develop a more positive perception of the product as they feel it offers benefits commensurate with the sacrifices they make (Karna, Hansen & Juslin, 2003).

Purchase intention is also influenced by consumer value perception, a key factor in decision-making (Kong et al., 2014). Consumers tend to be more inclined to purchase products that provide added value and satisfaction in line with their expectations. In the context of energy-efficient electronic products, sustainable values and energy efficiency are expected to be determining factors in consumer value perception. However, there has been limited research specifically exploring how the green marketing mix can affect consumer value perception of these products.

Steg et al., (2014) found that consumers with a high perception of value for environmentally-friendly products tend to have stronger preferences and intentions to purchase such products. When consumers perceive long-term benefits from the product, including a positive environmental impact, they are more motivated to take purchasing actions. In the context of e-commerce platforms, Turban et al., (2015) state that factors like online shopping convenience, trust in the platform, and ease of use also contribute to consumer purchase intent through e-commerce.

In the context of e-commerce platforms, it is assumed that the green marketing mix can directly influence purchase intention and also mediate through value perception (Chen, Chen & Tung, 2018). In other words, the green marketing mix can influence consumers to form a positive perception of the product's value, which in turn motivates them to be more likely to purchase the product (Tan et al., 2022). This is reinforced by the research of Nekmahmud et al., (2022) which shows that the green marketing mix significantly influences purchase intention through value perception.

Value perception plays a mediating role in the influence of green marketing mix on purchase intention for energy-efficient electronic products (Wu & Chen, 2014). This mediation concept is based on the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) theory proposed by Petty & Cacioppo (1986). According to ELM, when consumers are influenced by marketing messages, they undergo elaboration processes through two routes: the central route and the peripheral route. The central route involves deep thinking and analysis of the information provided, while the peripheral route focuses more on peripheral factors such as visual and emotional aspects.

Meanwhile, Jinan, Surachman & Djumahir (2022) in their findings indicate that green marketing does not have a significant direct influence on purchase intention. However, it has a significant indirect influence through value perception. In this study, value perception plays a crucial role in mediating the relationship between green marketing and purchase intention.

Green marketing has become an increasingly popular strategy amid growing environmental concerns (Laroche, Bergeron & Barbaro-Forleo, 2001). Moreover, recent research has also highlighted the moderating role of value perception in linking the green marketing mix to purchase intention (Mahmoud et al., 2017). Thus, green marketing has become a relevant and important topic in companies' efforts to have a positive impact on consumer purchasing behavior.

There is a complex relationship among the key variables, namely green marketing mix, value perception, and purchase intention through e-commerce. Additionally, the role of e-commerce platforms in facilitating product purchases has become increasingly significant. In

recent years, transactions through e-commerce have seen a significant increase. However, there is limited research examining how the green marketing mix can influence consumer purchase intention through e-commerce platforms, especially for energy-efficient electronic products.

Nevertheless, there is still a lack of in-depth research on the influence of green marketing mix on consumer value perception in the context of energy-efficient electronic products and how it affects purchase intention through e-commerce platforms. Therefore, this research aims to fill this knowledge gap by investigating the impact of green marketing mix on consumer value perception and purchase intention through e-commerce platforms, specifically for energy-efficient electronic products. This study will test the mediating role of value perception in the relationship between green marketing mix and purchase intention.

The results of this research are expected to provide a deeper insight into the mechanisms of how green marketing mix influences purchase intention through the formation of value perception. It will also contribute to the theoretical understanding of the interactions among these variables. This can certainly be achieved by embracing these concepts to explore the relationship between green marketing mix, value perception, and purchase intention through e-commerce in the context of energy-efficient electronic products.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Green Marketing Mix

Kotler & Keller (2012) explained that the Green Marketing Mix plays a role in influencing consumers' perceptions of a product's sustainability. The elements of the Green Marketing Mix can motivate consumers to choose more environmentally-friendly products.

The Green Marketing Mix is a strategic marketing approach that emphasizes elements contributing to environmental sustainability. This concept comprises four main elements: Green Product, Fair Price, Efficient Distribution, and Sustainable Promotion. This approach enables companies to communicate sustainability values to consumers, with the hope of influencing their perceptions of products and motivating purchase actions.

2.2. Value Perception

Steg et al., (2014) stated that value perception significantly influences consumers' preferences for environmentally-friendly products. Consumers tend to prefer products that offer long-term benefits, including a positive environmental impact.

Value perception is an individual's perspective on the benefits obtained from a product or service compared to the sacrifices they have to make, whether in terms of money, time, or effort. Value perception affects how consumers evaluate a product and whether they feel the product is worth the investment they make. In the context of this research, value perception focuses on how consumers assess energy-efficient electronic products from the standpoint of environmental benefits and energy efficiency.

2.3. Purchase Intentions

The study by Turban et al., (2015) indicates that factors such as online shopping convenience, trust in e-commerce platforms, and ease of use contribute to consumer purchase intention.

Purchase intention refers to the inclination or determination of consumers to make a purchase of a product or service. In today's digital era, e-commerce platforms have become a crucial means for consumers to carry out shopping activities. Previous research has identified factors

influencing purchase intention through e-commerce, such as online shopping convenience, transaction security, and ease of navigation within the platform.

3. Research Method

This study is a hypothesis-testing research that aims to explain specific influences using a causal approach, which seeks explanations in the form of relationships among several concepts, variables, or strategies developed in management (Sekaran, 2006). This research seeks causal relationships between the independent variable, the green marketing mix, and value perception and purchase intention through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram.

Population refers to the collection of elements in the form of events, things, or individuals with similar characteristics that are the focus of a researcher's attention and are considered the universe of the study (Ferdinand, 2014). The population in this research consists of all users of the e-commerce platform who have conducted transactions for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram.

A sample, according to Ferdinand (2014), is a subset of the population, consisting of several members of the population. This subset is selected because in many cases, it is not possible to study the entire population; therefore, we form a representative sample of the population. The sample size established in this research consists of 100 respondents. Roscoe (as cited in Ferdinand, 2014) states that a sample size larger than 30 respondents and less than 500 respondents is adequate for most research.

The sampling technique used in this research is Non-Probability Sampling because there is no complete sampling frame as the exact population size is unknown. The type of sampling employed is purposive sampling, which is the selection of a sample using specific considerations tailored to the research objectives or the research problem being developed (Ferdinand, 2014).

The data collection instrument used in this research is an online questionnaire. The questionnaire presented in this research consists of statements regarding the influence of the Green Marketing Mix on Value Perception and Purchase Intention through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. The questionnaire is distributed to respondents online via Google Forms.

Data analysis with statistics is conducted using SEM-PLS with the assistance of the SmartPLS software. The advantages of analysis using PLS, according to Wold (as cited in Ghozali & Latan, 2015), include that PLS is a powerful analysis method because it is not based on many assumptions. Data does not have to follow multivariate normal distribution (indicators with categorical, ordinal, interval, and even ratio scales) and can be used in the same model, and the sample does not have to be large. PLS can analyze both reflective and formative constructs simultaneously, which is not possible in CBSEM as it would result in an unidentified model.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Data Analysis

Before conducting the analysis using the Partial Least Squares (PLS) method, data analysis is performed. The data analysis technique employed to analyze the data in this research is the scoring method using a Likert scale. The statement alternatives, for instance, range from agree to disagree, satisfied to dissatisfied, happy to unhappy, and so forth. Responses from the list of statements (questionnaire) that have been created are evaluated by creating a 5-level Likert scale.

Descriptive data provides an identification of respondents' responses to the statements in the questionnaire. In this study,

descriptive statistics of responses to the questionnaire include data descriptions of respondents' answers to the indicators of each variable under investigation. These variables include the green marketing mix variable with 12 indicators, the value perception variable with 3 indicators, and the purchase intention variable with 4 indicators. Through the research results, respondents' answers to the questionnaire can be determined and presented in tabular form. To determine the category of respondents' answers, the average value of the respondents' answers is examined.

TABLE I. FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION SCORES

Variable	Score	Criteria
Green Marketing Mix (X)	4.27	Very Good
Value Perception (Z)	4.16	Good
Purchase Intentions (Y)	4.18	Good

Source: data analysis results.

In Table I, the responses of 100 respondents to the components of the green marketing mix variable perceived by e-commerce platform users in Mataram are presented. These responses are based on the respondents' feedback on each item of the variable statements. This component consists of 12 statement indicators related to the dimensions of green product, green price, green place, and green promotion. It can be categorized that the green marketing mix for e-commerce platform users in Mataram is considered excellent. This is evidenced by respondents' answers, indicating an average total score of 4.27, falling within the criteria of excellence ranging from 4.20 to 5.00.

Next, for value perception perceived by e-commerce platform users in Mataram. The value perception variable consists of three statement indicators, which describe functional value, emotional value, and self-expression value. In general, it can be explained that value perception for e-commerce platform users in Mataram is good. This is supported by respondents' answers, reflecting an average total score of 4.16, which falls within the criteria of goodness ranging from 3.40 to 4.19.

The responses from 100 respondents regarding the purchase intention variable through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram are presented, based on their responses to each statement item presented. Based on the table, it can be categorized that customers' purchase intention is good. This variable comprises four statement indicators representing transactional interest, referential interest, preferential interest, and exploratory interest. Looking at the average values of the purchase intention variable with its 4 item indicators, measured on an interval scale where 1 is the lowest and 5 is the highest, it can be explained through the average values of each indicator, which are 4.18, falling within the criteria of goodness ranging from 3.40 to 4.19.

Data processing using the SEM-based PLS method requires two stages in assessing the Model Fit of a research model (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). There are three criteria for using the data analysis technique with SmartPLS to assess the Outer Model: Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity, and Composite Reliability.

Convergent Validity of the measurement model is assessed based on the correlation between item scores or component scores estimated with SmartPLS software. Individual reflective measures are considered high if they correlate above 0.70 with the measured variable. However, according to Chin (as cited in Ghozali & Latan, 2015), for preliminary scale measurement in research, loading values of 0.50 to 0.60 are considered sufficiently adequate. In this study, a loading factor threshold of 0.60 is used.

The results of processing using PLS can be seen in Table II. The outer model values or correlations between indicators and variables that have met the convergent validity criteria, as they have loading factor

values above 0.60, can be further analyzed, while those that do not meet the criteria are not included in further analysis.

TABLE II. OUTER LOADINGS (MEASUREMENT MODEL)

No.	Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading
1	Green Marketing Mix (X)	X _{1.01}	0.637
		X _{1.02}	0.652
		X _{1.03}	0.637
		X _{1.04}	0.618
		X _{1.05}	0.674
		X _{1.06}	0.680
		X _{1.07}	0.720
		X _{1.08}	0.750
		X _{1.09}	0.856
		X _{1.10}	0.702
		X _{1.11}	0.771
		X _{1.12}	0.694
2	Value Perception (Z)	Z _{1.01}	0.780
		Z _{1.02}	0.790
		Z _{1.03}	0.823
3	Purchase Intentions (Y)	Y _{1.01}	0.855
		Y _{1.02}	0.870
		Y _{1.03}	0.893
		Y _{1.04}	0.913

Source: data analysis results.

Table II shows that all green marketing mix indicators have outer loading values greater than 0.60. Indicator X_{1.09} is the strongest measure of the green marketing mix variable as it has the highest outer loading value (0.856). Therefore, it can be stated that all twelve indicators are valid as measures of the green marketing mix variable.

For the value perception variable, it is demonstrated that there are three indicators with outer loading values greater than 0.60. Indicator Z_{1.03} is the strongest measure of the value perception variable as it has the highest outer loading value (0.823). Thus, it can be stated that the three indicators used are valid as measures of the value perception.

Furthermore, by considering the average values in the purchase intention variable, there are four indicators with outer loading values greater than 0.60. Indicator Y_{1.04} is the strongest measure of the Purchase Intention variable as it has the highest outer loading value (0.913). This result indicates that transactional interest, referential interest, preferential interest, and exploratory interest are strong indicators in measuring Purchase Intention. Therefore, all indicators used are considered valid, allowing the data in this study to be further analyzed.

Discriminant validity is conducted to ensure that each concept of each latent variable is distinct from other variables. The model is said to have good discriminant validity if each indicator loading value of a latent variable has a higher loading value when correlated with other latent variables. The results of the discriminant validity test are presented in Table III:

TABLE III. DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY

	Average Variance Extracted		Correlation		
	AVE	AVE Root	Green Marketing Mix (X)	Value Perception (Z)	Purchase Intentions (Y)
Green Marketing Mix (X)	0.493	0.702	1.000		
Value Perception (Z)	0.636	0.798	0.713	1.000	
Purchase Intentions (Y)	0.779	0.883	0.742	0.664	1.000

Source: data analysis results.

Based on Table III, it can be explained that from the analysis results, the Value Perception and Purchase Intention variables have Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values above 0.50, while the green marketing mix is still within the tolerance limit approaching a value of 0.50, specifically 0.493. This means that the latent variable green marketing mix can explain on average almost half of the variance of its indicators. Discriminant validity of the reflective model is evaluated through cross-loading, then compared AVE values with the square of the correlation between constructs (or comparing the square root of AVE with the inter-construct correlations).

Cross-loading measures compare the correlation of indicators with their construct and with constructs from other blocks. If the correlation between an indicator and its construct is higher than the correlation with constructs from other blocks, it indicates that the construct predicts the measure in their block better than other blocks. Another measure of discriminant validity is that the square root of AVE should be higher than the correlation between constructs or AVE values should be higher than the square of the inter-construct correlations. Thus, all variables have square root AVE values higher than the coefficients of correlation between one variable and another, indicating that the data has good discriminant validity.

The criteria for validity and reliability can also be seen from the reliability values of a variable and the AVE values of each variable. A variable is considered to have high reliability if the composite reliability value is above 0.70, and AVE is above 0.50. Table IV presents the values of Composite Reliability.

TABLE IV. COMPOSITE RELIABILITY

Variable	Composite Reliability
Green Marketing Mix (X)	0.921
Value Perception (Z)	0.840
Purchase Intentions (Y)	0.934

Source: data analysis results.

Table IV informs that all variables meet the composite reliability as their values are above the recommended threshold (> 0.70), which means that all research variables meet the reliability criteria.

Based on the overall evaluation results, including convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability as previously discussed, it can be concluded that the indicators measuring latent variables are valid and reliable.

The inner model or structural model testing is conducted to examine the relationships between variables, the significance values, and the R-square of the research model. The structural model is evaluated using R-square for dependent variables, t-tests, and the significance of the structural path coefficient.

The assessment of the model with PLS begins by examining the R-square for each dependent latent variable. Changes in the R-square value can be used to assess the influence of specific exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables that have substantive effects. Table V displays the estimation results of R-square using SmartPLS.

TABLE V. R-SQUARE VALUE

Variable	R-Square
Value Perception (Z)	0.508
Purchase Intentions (Y)	0.588

Source: data analysis results.

Table V shows the R-square values for the value perception variable as 0.508 and for the purchase intention variable as 0.588. The higher the R-square value, the greater the ability of the exogenous variable to be

explained by the endogenous variable, indicating a better fit for the structural equations constructed in the research model. For the value perception variable, it has an R-square value of 0.508 (moderate), meaning that 50.80 percent of the variance in value perception is explained by the green marketing mix variable, while the remaining variance is explained by variables outside the research model. The purchase intention variable has an R-square value of 0.588 (moderate), indicating that 58.80 percent of the variance in purchase intention is explained by the green marketing mix and value perception variables, while the remaining variance is explained by variables outside the research model.

From Figure 1, it can be explained that the covariance of measurement indicators is influenced by latent constructs or reflects variations of the unidimensional constructs depicted in circular shapes with several arrows from constructs to indicators. This model hypothesizes that changes in latent constructs affect changes in indicators. In the model, there is one exogenous variable, green marketing mix, one intervening endogenous variable, value perception, and one dependent endogenous variable, purchase intention.

FIGURE 1. STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL

The significance of the estimated parameters provides valuable information about the relationships between research variables. The basis for hypothesis testing is the values found in the output result for inner weights. Table VI provides the estimation output for testing the structural model.

TABLE VI. RESULT FOR INNER WEIGHTS

Variable	Original Sample	Standard Error	T Statistics	P Values	Conclusion
Green Marketing Mix (X) → Value Perception (Z)	0.713	0.067	10.657	0.000	Accepted
Green Marketing Mix (X) → Purchase Intentions (Y)	0.547	0.118	4.647	0.000	Accepted
Value Perception (Z) → Purchase Intentions (Y)	0.274	0.119	2.308	0.021	Accepted

Source: data analysis results.

Hypothesis 1 states that green marketing mix has a positive and significant impact on value perception. The test results of the parameter

coefficient between green marketing mix and value perception show a positive relationship with a coefficient value of 0.713, a t-statistic value of 10.657, and significance at $\alpha = 0.050$. The t-statistic value is above the critical value of 1.960, thus, H_a is accepted, indicating a significant influence of green marketing mix on value perception. This implies that one of the determinants of value perception among users of e-commerce platforms for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram is green marketing mix. If green marketing mix is high, then value perception among users of e-commerce platforms for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram is high, and vice versa if green marketing mix is low, then value perception among users of e-commerce platforms for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram is also low.

Hypothesis 2 states that green marketing mix has a positive and significant impact on purchase intention. The test results of the parameter coefficient between green marketing mix and purchase intention show a positive relationship with a coefficient value of 0.547, a t-statistic value of 4.647, and significance at $\alpha = 0.050$. The t-statistic value is above the critical value of 1.960, thus, H_a is accepted, indicating a significant influence of green marketing mix on purchase intention through e-commerce platforms for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. The level of purchase intention through e-commerce platforms for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram can be determined by the level of green marketing mix; the higher the green marketing mix, the higher the purchase intention, and conversely, if the green marketing mix is low, then the purchase intention is also low.

Hypothesis 3 states that value perception has a positive and significant impact on purchase intention. The test results of the parameter coefficient between value perception and purchase intention show a positive relationship with a coefficient value of 0.274, a t-statistic value of 2.308, and significance at $\alpha = 0.050$. The t-statistic value is above the critical value of 1.960, thus, H_a is accepted, indicating that value perception has a positive and significant impact on purchase intention through e-commerce platforms for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. This means that an increase in value perception leads to an increase in purchase intention, and conversely, if value perception is perceived as poor or not good, it leads to a decrease in purchase intention.

The magnitude of the indirect effect of the green marketing mix variable on purchase intention through the value perception variable is obtained by multiplying the path coefficients (beta) between the direct effect of green marketing mix on value perception and the direct effect of value perception on purchase intention through e-commerce platforms for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. The magnitude of the influence of green marketing mix on purchase intention with the mediation of the value perception variable is 0.195 (0.713×0.274). For a clearer view of the magnitude of the mediating variable/influence between the independent variable green marketing mix and purchase intention through the mediation of the value perception variable, refer to Table VII below:

TABLE VII. DIRECT EFFECT AND INDIRECT EFFECT

Effect	Formula	Result
Direct Effect		
Green Marketing Mix (X) → Value Perception (Z)	-	0.713
Value Perception (Z) → Purchase Intentions (Y)	-	0.274
Indirect Effect		
Green Marketing Mix (X) → Value Perception (Z) → Purchase Intentions (Y)	(0.713×0.274)	0.195

Source: data analysis results.

Thus, it is known that the green marketing mix variable indirectly influences purchase intention through e-commerce platforms for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram by mediating the value perception variable, with a coefficient value of 0.195. This result indicates that there is a significant indirect influence of green marketing mix on purchase intention through e-commerce platforms for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram with the mediation of value perception.

Based on the Partial Least Square analysis results with SmartPLS, the coefficient value for value perception is 0.274, which is smaller than the green marketing mix coefficient of 0.713. This means that 27.40 percent of purchase intention through e-commerce platforms for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram is influenced by value perception. From this research, it can be concluded that green marketing mix is more dominant in increasing purchase intention compared to value perception. This indicates that value perception has a lower influence on purchase intention compared to green marketing mix.

4.2. Research Findings and Discussions

Based on the PLS analysis results, this section discusses the calculations that have been conducted. The purpose of this research is to determine the influence of green marketing mix on purchase intention with the mediation of value perception among users of e-commerce platforms for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. The testing is demonstrated through the existing hypotheses to understand how each variable affects the others.

The results of the data analysis show that green marketing mix has a positive and significant effect on value perception. This finding is in line with the opinion of Karna, Hansen & Juslin (2003), who stated that there is a significant positive influence between green marketing mix and value perception. When green marketing mix is applied effectively to a product, it can lead to an increase in value perception towards the offered product. Similarly, Prothero & Fitchett (2000) explained that green marketing mix is closely related to value perception.

The findings in this study also confirm the views of Pujari, Wright & Peattie (2003), where green marketing mix, measured through four dimensions: green product, green price, green place, and green promotion, can significantly enhance value perception. This provides evidence that the research hypothesis is accepted. The green marketing mix applied by e-commerce platforms has a positive and significant impact on the value perception of e-commerce platform users for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. The way green marketing mix is applied, based on the direct benefits perceived by customers, has a positive and significant impact on value perception. This implies that the higher and increased green marketing mix, the higher the value perception of e-commerce platform users for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram.

This research is consistent with the studies conducted by Karna, Hansen & Juslin (2003) and Prothero & Fitchett (2000). Based on this research, it can be explained that green marketing mix indeed significantly influences the level of value perception in individuals. The higher green marketing mix contributes to an increase in value perception, although value perception itself is relative or varies from one person to another. These results can be understood because they align with the concept that value perception is a state in which e-commerce platform users in Mataram feel satisfied while using energy-efficient electronic products because their needs, desires, and expectations regarding electronic products are met.

Based on the data analysis results, there is a positive and significant influence of green marketing mix on purchase intention. This result indicates that the opinion put forward by Kong et al., (2014), where purchase intention is influenced by green marketing mix, is valid.

This is in line with the findings in the research conducted by Ashoush & Kortam (2022), where green marketing mix can increase purchase intention.

Based on the results of this research, it can be interpreted that the applied green marketing mix significantly influences purchase intention through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. The data analysis results show that green marketing mix has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. This means that green marketing mix, measured through 12 indicator items, has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. Therefore, it is known that green marketing mix has a positive and significant impact on purchase intention. The better the application of green marketing mix by manufacturers to their products, the better the purchase intention for the produced products.

The findings of this research are also supported by previous studies, such as the one conducted by Kong et al., (2014) where green marketing mix has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. This proves that green marketing mix has a positive and significant impact on purchase intention through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. Based on this research, it can be explained that green marketing mix is indeed crucial for companies to implement in their products to achieve high purchase intention and meet one of the criteria set by environmental organizations.

The data analysis results show that value perception, measured through three indicators, namely functional value, emotional value, and self-expression value, has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. This implies that as value perception increases, customers experience an increase in purchase intention through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. Conversely, if value perception towards a product is low, then purchase intention through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram towards the product decreases.

The findings in this research further reinforce the opinions put forward by Chan (1999) and Ottman (2011) that environmentally conscious consumers tend to have a strong environmental concern and prefer environmentally friendly products over others. It also confirms the findings of Kong et al., (2014) which state that value perception can lead to purchase intention. If customers with good value perception increase, then purchase intention can also be increased, thus validating the hypotheses in this research.

This research aligns with previous studies, including Wu & Chen (2014). Their research results indicate that value perception has a positive influence on purchase intention. Based on this research, it can be explained that value perception indeed significantly influences the level of purchase intention in a customer, although value perception itself is highly relative and varies among individuals.

Based on the results presented, this study concludes that purchase intention is indirectly influenced by the green marketing mix variable through the value perception variable, where the percentage contribution of the value given is relatively significant. This finding can confirm the opinion put forward by Mahmoud et al., (2017) where effective green marketing mix can enhance value perception and ultimately lead to an increase in purchase intention. The research results are also supported by the study of Chen, Chen & Tung (2018), which states that green marketing mix can enhance value perception, and customers with a positive perception are customers with a high level of purchase intention.

The results of this research further reinforce the theoretical framework proposed by Jinan, Surachman & Djumahir (2022); Nekomahmud et al., (2022); Tan et al., (2022), where their findings indicate that a good green marketing mix generates a positive value perception of the offered products and ultimately increases purchase intention. This finding provides guidance for energy-efficient electronic

product companies in managing their green marketing mix. Green marketing mix can influence purchase intention through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram with the mediation of value perception. This means that the higher the green marketing mix applied to the product, the higher the value perception, which ultimately improves purchase intention through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram.

Based on the results shown, the R-square indicates that purchase intention is influenced by two variables, green marketing mix and value perception. Both of these independent variables provide a relatively moderate percentage contribution (58.80 percent) because of other factors not included in the research model. This finding provides guidance for energy-efficient electronic product companies in managing their customers' purchase intention to increase it and maintain it. A customer's value perception is also influenced by various factors that also affect a person's purchase intention in using energy-efficient electronic products. This R-square value could increase in the future with several alternatives that can be implemented by manufacturers, one of which is collaboration with organizations/institutions concerned with the environment.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research results on respondents who use the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram, the following conclusions can be drawn: 1) Green marketing mix has a positive and significant effect on value perception. This indicates that the better the green marketing mix implemented by energy-efficient electronic product companies, the higher the value perception of customers. Conversely, if the green marketing mix is low or declining, it can reduce the level of value perception; 2) Green marketing mix has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. This means that the better the green marketing mix, the higher the purchase intention through the e-commerce platform for energy-efficient electronic products in Mataram. Conversely, if the green marketing mix is low, it will negatively impact the level of purchase intention; 3) Value perception has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. This result proves that the better the value perception of energy-efficient electronic products, the higher the purchase intention. Conversely, if the value perception is lower, the purchase intention will also decrease.

Based on the discussion and conclusions presented earlier, the recommendations from this study are as follows: companies addressing the green marketing mix issue should continue to enhance the positive value of green marketing mix regarding the environment in the eyes of consumers, provide additional quality to improve consumer value perception, which will eventually build trust in energy-efficient electronic products. Manufacturers should provide more detailed and accurate information about the products offered, such as conducting online quizzes that can be used as a platform to disseminate information about the products. This will increase consumer knowledge about the products, especially in terms of green marketing and environmentally friendly products, making it easier for consumers to evaluate products to increase purchase interest, especially for consumers who are starting to switch to environmentally friendly products.

For future research, it is recommended to further develop and use more independent variables that influence consumer purchase intention as predictor variables, as both independent variables in this study only provide a moderate percentage contribution (58.80 percent). Subsequent researchers can incorporate other factors that were not used in the research model. This R-square value could increase in the future with the addition of several variables not used in this study.

Additionally, future researchers can involve a larger number of respondents because the larger the sample size or the closer it is to the population, the lower the chance of generalization errors, resulting in more accurate research conclusions.

References

- Ashoush, N., & Kortam, W. (2022). The impact of green marketing strategies on consumers' purchasing intention. *The Business and Management Review*, 13(2), 263-275. https://cberuk.com/cdn/conference_proceedings/2022-09-16-09-25-05-AM.pdf
- Chan, R. Y. K. (1999). Environmental attitudes and behaviour of consumer in China. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 11(4), 25-52. https://doi.org/10.1300/J046v11n04_03
- Chan, R. Y. K., Loret, B., & Lau, Y. (2000). Antecedents of green purchases: a survey in China. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 17(4), 338-357. <https://doi.org/10.1108/07363760010335358>
- Chen, C. C., Chen, C. W., & Tung, Y. C. (2018). Exploring the consumer behavior of intention to purchase green products in belt and road countries: an empirical analysis. *Sustainability Journal*, 10(854), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10030854>
- Cobb-Walgreen, C. J., Ruble, C. A., & Donthu, N. (1995). Brand equity, brand preference, and purchase intent. *Journal of Advertising*, 24(3), 25-40. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00913367.1995.10673481>
- Ferdinand, A. (2014). *Metode Penelitian Manajemen*. Semarang: Badan Penerbitan Universitas Diponegoro.
- Ghozali, I., & Latan, H. (2015). *Partial Least Squares: Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Menggunakan Program SmartPLS 3.0 untuk Penelitian Empiris*, Edisi 2. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Jinan, A. S. I., Surachman, & Djumahir. (2022). Analysis of the effect of green marketing and environmental knowledge on purchase intentions mediated by brand image. *International Journal of Environmental, Sustainability, and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 47-58. <https://doi.org/10.38142/ijess.v3i1.157>
- Karna, J., Hansen, E., & Juslin, H. (2003). Social responsibility in environmental marketing planning. *European Journal of Marketing*, 37(5), 848-871. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090560310465170>
- Kong, W., Harun, A., Sulong, R. S., & Lily, J. (2014). The influence of consumers perception of green product on green purchasing intention. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 4(8), 924-939. <https://archive.aessweb.com/index.php/5007/article/view/2688/4078>
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K.L. (2012). *Principle of Marketing*, Global Edition, 14th Edition. USA: Pearson Education Limited.
- Laroche, M., Bergeron, J., & Barbaro-Forleo, G. (2001). Targeting consumers who are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 18(6), 503-520. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EUM000000006155>
- Mahmoud, T. O. (2018). Impact of green marketing mix on purchase intention. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*, 5(2), 127-135. <https://doi.org/10.21833/ijaas.2018.02.020>
- Mahmoud, T. O., Ibrahim, S. B., Ali, A. H., & Bleadly, A. (2017). The influence of green marketing mix on purchase intention: The mediation role of environmental knowledge. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 8(9), 1040-1048. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14299/ijser.2017.09.006>
- Nekmahmud, M., Naz, F., Ramkissoon, H., & Fekete-Farkas, M. (2022). Transforming consumers' intention to purchase green products: Role of social media. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 185(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122067>

- Ottman, J. A. (2011). *The New Rules of Green Marketing: Strategies, Tools, and Inspiration for Sustainable Branding*. Sheffield, UK: Greenleaf Publishing.
http://www.greenmarketing.com/files/NRoGM_ch1REVIEW-COPY-FOR-FREE-DOWNLOAD.pdf
- Petty, R. E., & Cacioppo, J. T. (1986). *The Elaboration Likelihood Model of Persuasion*. In: *Communication and Persuasion*. Springer Series in Social Psychology. New York: Springer NY.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4612-4964-1_1
- Prothero, A., & Fitchett, J. A. (2000). Greening capitalism: opportunities for a green commodity. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 20(1), 46-55.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0276146700201005>
- Pujari, D., Wright, G., & Peattie, K. (2003). Green and competitive, influences on environmental new product development performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 56(8), 657-671.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963\(01\)00310-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963(01)00310-1)
- Rehman, Z. U., & Khyzer, M. (2013). Conceptualizing green purchasing intention in emerging market: an empirical analysis on Pakistan. *The 2013 WEI International Academic Conference Proceeding*, Istanbul, 99-120. <https://www.westeasinstitute.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/07/Zia-ur-Rehman.pdf>
- Sekaran, U. (2006). *Metodologi Penelitian Untuk Bisnis*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Steg, L., Perlaviciute, G., van der Werff, E., & Lurvink, J. (2014). The significance of hedonic values for environmentally relevant attitudes, preferences, and actions. *Environment and Behavior*, 46(2), 163-192. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916512454730>
- Tan, Z., Sadiq, B., Bashir, T., Mahmood, H., & Rasool, Y. (2022). Investigating the impact of green marketing components on purchase intention: the mediating role of brand image and brand trust. *Sustainability*, 14(1), 1-15.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su14105939>
- Turban, E., King, D., Lee, J. K., Liang, T. P., & Turban, D. C. (2015). *Electronic Commerce: A Managerial and Social Networks Perspective*. In: *Springer Texts in Business and Economics*, 8th Edition. London: Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10091-3>
- Wu, S. I., & Chen, Y. J. (2014). The impact of green marketing and perceived innovation on purchase intention for green products. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 6(5), 81-100.
<https://doi.org/10.5539/ijms.v6n5p81>